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A hybrid approach for the detection of retinal lesions in fundus photography using computer vision and image processing

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Abstract

Retinal lesions are a leading cause of preventable vision loss among working adults worldwide. The progression of retinal lesions often results in irreversible vision loss, highlighting the criticality of early identification. However, the conventional diagnosis relies on ophthalmologists examining the fundus image to identify lesions, which is time-consuming, highly subjective, and limited by the shortage of experts to accommodate the rising demand. In response to these challenges, computer-aided retinal lesion detection systems have been developed, yet they struggle to achieve reliable accuracy and robustness when applied to real-world data. Variations in image quality, data scarcity and class imbalance, diversity of lesions, and the subtle appearance of small lesions lead to missed detections and poor generalization across datasets. This research proposes a deep learning-based object detection framework that integrates computer vision and image processing techniques to identify and localize retinal lesions in fundus images. The model aims to localize and classify multiple lesion types, including microaneurysms, hemorrhages, hard exudates and soft exudates, directly from fundus images. The study employs an anchor-free detection approach, combined with transfer learning, data augmentation, and a series of complementary pre-processing and post-processing techniques tailored to the biological characteristics of lesions, to improve lesion visibility and contrast. This approach is expected to achieve enhanced accuracy, robustness, and generalizability. The expected outcome is a detection framework that can achieve higher accuracy, better robustness, and improved generalization compared to existing systems. The findings from this research are expected to highlight the potential of integrating deep learning and image processing for improved diagnostic reliability. This approach will enhance the generalizability, robustness, and accuracy while maintaining computational efficiency, offering broader insights into medical imaging and small object detection. Ultimately, the proposed system aims to reduce the clinical burden by facilitating the automatic detection of retinal lesions and identifying retinal abnormalities early, thereby preventing vision loss.

Keywords: Computer Vision, Fundus imaging, Image Processing, Object detection, Retinal lesion detection

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1. Introduction

Retinal lesions are areas of damage caused by leakage of blood or fluids from damaged retinal blood vessels (Alyoubi, Abulkhair and Shalash, 2021). These lesions are primary indicators of conditions that eventually result in irreversible vision loss, such as diabetic retinopathy, hypertension and severe anaemia, making their timely and accurate detection crucial (Santos et al., 2022). According to the International Diabetes Federation, global prevalence of diabetes is projected to increase to about 693 million by 2045, and one-third will have diabetic retinopathy (Sebastian et al., 2023). Consequently, the demand for diagnosis is significantly higher, with an estimated three million people being examined daily (Steffi and Sam Emmanuel, 2024). However, as a standard, ophthalmologists manually examine the fundus photo to identify lesions. This heavily relies on expert knowledge, can be time-consuming, subjective, and labour-intensive (Sebastian et al., 2023).

Automated systems that have emerged in response to this have significant limitations, despite the evolution of computational approaches and medical imaging, rendering the accurate detection of retinal lesions a critical unresolved issue (Li et al., 2019). The majority of the existing research missed the detection of microaneurysms due to their minute size and subtlety (Steffi and Sam Emmanuel, 2024). Lesions are often confused with regular anatomical structures, such as blood vessels and the optic disk (Sebastian et al., 2023). Image quality degradations caused by uneven illumination, noise, and artefacts compromise the reliability (Tsiknakis et al., 2021; Santos et al., 2022). Furthermore, the lesions can vary in type, size, and appearance, implying that it is inherently problematic to precisely detect and isolate them (Sebastian et al., 2023). This research, therefore, aims to develop and evaluate a deep learning-based object detection system that integrates image processing techniques to achieve improved accuracy, robustness, and clinical applicability in the detection of retinal lesions.

2. Methodology

This research will employ a quantitative experimental design that integrates image processing and deep learning techniques for retinal lesion detection. The proposed detection framework consists of sequential stages, including dataset selection, pre-processing, model selection, model training, post-processing, testing, evaluation, and iterative optimization of the model based on the results obtained. The diagram below outlines the entire workflow.

Figure 01: System pipeline block diagram

The Diabetic Retinopathy Detection dataset (DDR dataset) will be used, which includes 757 fundus images with bounding box annotations and class labels for microaneurysms, haemorrhages, hard exudates, and soft exudates (Li et al., 2019).

2.1 Pre-processing

Fundus images exhibit noise and variations due to differences in illumination, environmental conditions and capturing devices, making the image quality distortions inevitable (Tsiknakis et al., 2021). Pre-processing enhances lesion visibility and model performance using complementary techniques such as Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE), green-channel extraction, normalization, and noise reduction filters. Several variants, CLAHE only, CLAHE + green channel, and raw images, will be compared to identifying the most effective combination.

2.2 Algorithm Selection

YOLO is a state-of-the-art object detection framework used across numerous application domains, renowned for its speed, adaptability to novel domains, ease of integration and robust ecosystem (Ragab et al., 2024). YOLOv8, a single-stage, anchor-free variant of the YOLO family, is selected due to its improved efficiency, accuracy, and refined architecture. It is trained with transfer learning on 640×640 inputs for 100 epochs using the Adam optimizer, with a batch size of 16 and a learning rate of 0.001.

Post-processing techniques will be employed to refine the detection outputs, reduce false positives, and merge fragmented detections.

This methodology aims to establish an accurate, robust, and systematic framework for detecting retinal lesions, with potential applicability in clinical screening and diagnostic support.

3. Data Analysis and Results

3.1 Data Analysis

The experimental analysis will utilise the DDR dataset, selected following a comparative assessment of the Tonji Diabetic Retinopathy dataset (TJDR), Indian Diabetic Retinopathy Image Dataset (IDRiD), E-Opatha, and Asia Pacific Tele-Ophthalmology Society 2019 Blindness Detection (APTOS 2019 BD) datasets in terms of dataset size and bounding box annotations, which best complement the proposed hybrid model’s performance.

A structured survey with closed questions was conducted to understand the user perceptions and prioritise the requirements of the proposed system. Survey results indicated limited public awareness of retinal lesions and fundus imaging, despite finding the screening important. Most of the participants exhibited lifestyle patterns that could aggravate retinal lesions and preferred accessing the system via the clinics and as a self-service tool. The results highlighted the user perception of the proposed system as an early diagnosis tool, with misinterpretation of results identified as a key concern.

Model predictions will be compared with ground-truth bounding box annotations to evaluate detection accuracy using established object detection metrics.

Table 01: Performance metrics

Metric	Description	Purpose
Intersection over Union (IoU)	To measure the predicted and ground truth overlap	Evaluate the detection accuracy.
Average Precision (AP)	To capture the tradeoff via the area under the precision-recall curve	Assess the detection quality per class.
Mean Average Precision (mAP)	Average AP across all classes at IoU thresholds (0.5:0.95)	Assess the overall model performance.
Area under the Precision-Recall curve (AUPR)	Integrates precision and recall across all confidence levels.	Evaluate the capability of maximising True positives.

3.2 Expected Results

The proposed hybrid pipeline is expected to demonstrate measurable performance improvements compared to baseline models by combining image processing techniques for pre-processing and post-processing. Model performance will be tested on the DDR

test split using a standard evaluation protocol where predictions are matched to ground truth bounding boxes across lesion classes at IoU thresholds ranging from 0.5 to 0.95.

The expected outcomes include a higher mAP compared to a baseline YOLOv8 model trained without image processing modules, a stronger precision-recall balance specifically for microaneurysms and exudates where existing models limited their performance, and improved AUPR with enhanced visibility and greater robustness under variable image quality through post-processing and pre-processing.

The outcomes will be achieved under uniform training conditions to ensure that the performance improvements stem solely from the design of the hybrid model, rather than variations in model training. Ultimately, the evaluation of the anticipated results aims to verify that the hybrid approach enhances the accurate detection of lesions, with improved robustness and generalisation compared to baseline models.

4. Discussion

The proposed methodology is expected to enhance the accuracy, robustness, and reliability of retinal lesion detection by aligning image processing techniques with lesion characteristics, thereby improving visibility and differentiation. However, class imbalance and image quality degradations may affect the robustness and generalisation of the model. As a mitigation strategy, data augmentation and transfer learning techniques will be utilised. Moreover, the literature emphasises that detecting microaneurysms remains challenging despite technological advancements. From a clinical perspective, the risks of false negatives, model transparency, and data privacy considerations will be acknowledged. In general, this framework has the potential to enhance the diagnostic efficiency of retinal screening, providing a foundation for automated lesion detection in future diagnostics.

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

The study demonstrates that a hybrid framework combining lesion-specific preprocessing and post-processing with a YOLO-based object detection model can significantly improve the detection of retinal lesions in fundus imaging. The hybrid design enhances lesion visibility, facilitates better lesion differentiation, addresses class imbalance, image quality degradation, and the subtlety of microaneurysms.

This system positions itself as an early diagnostic tool or an assistive tool, rather than replacing clinical expertise. The integration of this system into retinal screening workflows can reduce the burden on clinicians, improve the capacity of low-resource clinical ecosystems and contribute to improved healthcare outcomes.

Future work should involve expanding datasets that represent diverse retinal diseases and populations to further improve generalisability, integrating explainable AI to establish transparency and clinical trust, and obtaining expert validation of the predictions produced by the system. Through these advancements, this work strengthens the foundation for retinal screening systems that can narrow the gap between timely diagnosis and preventable vision loss.

6. References

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